
Project no. **H2020-SMEINST-2-726607**

Project Acronym: **Fastprk-2**

Project title: Enhanced on-street parking management system

Start date of project: 01.06.2016

Duration: 26 months

Project coordinator: Dr. Francisco Hernández-Ramírez

Project coordinator organization: Worldsensing SL

Project website address: <http://fastprk2.eu/>

Deliverable 6.2

Exploitation / dissemination activities report (year 2)

A. Dissemination Level

PU **Public**

- PP Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
- RE Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
- CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

B. Document details

Work Package	6
Partners	Worldsensing SL
Authors	Dr. Andrea Bartoli, Dr. Francisco Hernández-Ramírez, Dr. Xavi Vilajosana, Dr. Ignasi Vilajosana, Mr. Jose Gorchs & the Engineering, Marketing and Commercial Departments.
Document ID	6.2
Release Date	17/08/2018

C. Revision history

Version	Date	Changes	Author
1.0	17.08.2018	-	Dr. Francisco Hernández-Ramírez

Table of content

0. Executive Summary.....	5
1. Introduction.....	6
2. Analysis of impact KPIs (entire project).....	7
3. Successful impact activities.....	9
3.1 Documentation delivery.....	9
3.2 Workshops attended.....	9
3.3 Reports from end-users.....	9
3.4 Contribution to roadmaps.....	10
3.5 Contribution to policy-makers.....	11
3.6 Number of web users.....	12
3.7 Press releases.....	13
3.8 Domain exhibitions.....	14
3.9 Conference papers and presentations.....	19
3.10 Events attended.....	20
3.11 Business cases.....	25
3.12 Investors pitch.....	25
4. Fastprk2 Business Cases.....	26
4.1 Introduction.....	26
4.2 Fastprk2 concepts.....	27
4.3 Needs.....	28
Capitalize investments.....	28
Address political and social challenges.....	29
Guarantee the long-term flux of revenues.....	29
4.4 Market.....	30
4.5 Added value and innovation.....	31
4.6 Business Analysis.....	32
4.6.1 Clients.....	33
4.6.2 Competitors.....	33
4.6.3 Barriers.....	35
4.6.4 Marketing.....	35
4.6.5 Segmentation.....	36
4.7 Go-to-market strategy.....	36
4.7.1 Offer to client – three cases.....	36
4.7.2 Canvas – three cases.....	39
High quality on-street parking sensor. Product as a Service – PaaS.....	39
Advanced and interoperable mobility platform. Mobility as a Service - MaaS.....	41
Smart traffic and parking services. Software as a Service – SaaS.....	42

4.7.3 Income Forecast.....	44
Income forecast (aggregated figures) – Lower scenario	46
Income forecast (detail) – Lowe scenario.....	47
4.7.4 Conclusions	50
Abbreviation List.....	51
Annex I. IP generated in the frame of Fastprk2.....	52
Annex II. Surveys filled by pilots’ partners.....	54

0. Executive Summary

The ultimate aim of Fastprk2 has been to improve the smart parking technologies of Worldsensing. To that end, an innovative end-to-end on-street parking management system has been developed with better technical performances than competitors. Nevertheless, the success of any new product is conditional on the awareness that potential customers have of them. Hence, the spreading of the results and the parallel adaptation of the product characteristics to the customers' requirements is imperative. In this deliverable, the exploitation and dissemination actions undertaken during the second year of the project are reviewed, and the aggregated view for the whole action is provided. This work has become one of the core parts of the Fastprk2 activity once the pilots around Europe and the US have been running and they could be used as real demonstrators.

1. Introduction

Fastprk2 has resulted in a new smart parking product with better characteristics than those offered by the competitors. However, the successful market penetration strongly depends on the existing knowledge that stakeholders have of it. To guarantee this point, an active dissemination and exploitation plan have been conducted during the project execution period, gaining special weight in the last months (Y2). In fact, this has been a core part of Fastprk2 with a dedicated work package (WP6).

The deliverable overviews the exploitation and dissemination actions performed during the second period of the project and it is structured as follows: Chapter 1 reviews the project impact KPIs considering the results for the whole project, Chapter 3 presents the full list of actions of WP6 paying attention to those of the second period, and Chapter 4 covers the resulting business plans for the new product. Finally, supporting material is provided as an annex of the document.

The main conclusions drawn from the WP6 are positive with a remarkable impact of Fastprk2 in the smart parking community, and interesting contributions of the project to different scientific niche areas, such as the Data Science. Nevertheless, these activities will not end with the project and they are just the first step in the intense marketing campaign that Worldsensing is performing and which will continue in the future.

2. Analysis of impact KPIs (entire project)

The impact analysis of the project has been conducted through a detailed **KPIs analysis**. A set of them providing relevant, quantitative and measurable information of the project impact has been defined in the EC-GA, and they are grouped around the following five general objectives:

-Set the project's vision, scope, objectives and priorities: The KPIs in this context are:

-The % of tasks, deliverables, etc. that have been completed on time:	95%
-Number of work-shops attended:	3
-Reports from end-users:	5

-Policy impact: Continuous monitoring of policy development in Smart City clusters and activities in the European Innovation Framework as well as early identification of contributions to standards.

-Number of contributions to roadmaps, discussion papers:	2
-Number of contribution to policy-makers:	2

-Visibility of the project: The visibility of the project among the industrial sectors, citizens, the media and professional actors depends on the effectiveness of the dissemination. The following KPIs have been identified:

-Number of downloads of material from the website per year:	300
-Number of registered members of the website:	50
-Number of press releases issued:	4
-Number of domain exhibitions attended:	10

-Knowledge impact creation: The impact on creation and dissemination of knowledge generated in the project depends on a high level of activity in dissemination to the proper target groups.

-Number of journal publications:	2
-Number of conference papers and presentations:	4
-Number of events attended:	10

-Impact on Europe's technology leadership: The impact from the project's technological level on the global leadership and competitiveness of Europe's industry:

-Number of business cases elaborated:	3
-Participation to venture capitals and business angels' events:	3

An overview of the expected KPI values for the whole project against those really attained is shown below.

KPIs realization during the project agrees with the objectives envisaged in the EC-GA. Those KPIs with minor deviations from the milestone will be corrected during the next months (i.e., number of journal publications).

Activities and impact KPIs				
1-Project's vision, scope, objectives and priorities				
KPI	Planned	Done	%	Comment
1.1-The % of tasks, deliverables completed on time	95	100	100%	Completed
1.2-Number of work-shops attended	3	3	100%	Completed
1.3-Reports from end-users	5	6	100%	Completed
2-Policy impact				
KPI	Planned	Done	%	Comment
2.1-Number of contributions to roadmaps, discussion papers	2	2	100%	Completed
2.2-Number of contributions to policy-makers	2	2	100%	Completed
3-Visibility of the project				
KPI	Planned	Done	%	Comment
3.1-Number of downloads of material from the website per year	300	>300	100%	YouTube Fastprk2 videos display figures considered
3.2-Number of registered members of the website	50	50	100%	Completed
3.3-Number of press releases issued	4	14	100%	Completed
3.4-Number of domain exhibitions attended	10	10	100%	Completed
4-Knowledge impact creation				
KPI	Planned	Done	%	Comment
4.1-Number of journal publications	2	0	0%	Work in progress
4.2-Number of conference papers and presentations	4	4	100%	Completed
4.3-Number of events attended	10	10	100%	Completed
5-Impact on Europe's technology leadership				
KPI	Planned	Done	%	Comment
5.1-Number of business cases elaborated	3	3	100%	Completed
5.2-Participation to venture capitals and business angels' events	3	3	100%	Completed

3. Successful impact activities

In this section, the details that supports the KPIs realization are given providing evidence of the performed activities.

3.1 Documentation delivery

Action	Comments
1.1- The % of tasks, deliverables, etc. that have been completed on time	Fastprk2 reporting has been fully completed in agreement with the EC-GA provisions. For those deliverables with late submission, the approval from the EC-PO has been granted in advance.

3.2 Workshops attended

Action	Comments
1.2- Number of work-shops attended	Fastprk2 team has attended three workshops during the action. Details were provided in the deliverable D6.1.

3.3 Reports from end-users

Action	Comments
1.3-Number of reports from end-users	Worldsensing has collected six reports from the end-users in the frame of the pilot campaign.

During the first quarter of 2018, Worldsensing has conducted a validation process of the technology deployed at the project pilots, and to do this, the feedback from City Parking Group, ENGIE, SWARCO, UPC, Afapark and Parking Sense has been crucial. These partners have filled out a generic survey so that Worldsensing's marketing team can early identify the strengths and weaknesses of the new product.

Fastprk2 pilot brochure: this information document was distributed among the pilots' partners to provide a general overview of the test campaign.

The brochure is titled "fastprk2 PILOT PROJECT SCHEDULE 2017/18" and is divided into two main sections: "2. DETAILED SCHEDULE" and "1. AGENDA".

2. DETAILED SCHEDULE: This section explains that pilot installations and workshops are divided into two groups to guarantee a higher level of convenience and project quality. It includes a map of Europe with markers for partner locations and logos for ENGIE, AFAPARK, City Parking Group, SWARCO, and UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE CATALUNYA. Below the map, there are two columns of tables for "FIRST INSTALLATION" and "SECOND INSTALLATION", each with sub-tables for AFAPARK, City Parking Group, ENGIE, and SWARCO. These tables list "Use Case events" (Remote ID, Deployment, Workshop, Follow Up) and "Terminale date" for each partner.

1. AGENDA: This section lists high-level milestones during the pilot. Key milestones include:

- Finalizing pilot documentation (November).
- Initial session to present pilots and gather feedback (October).
- Plan and define timings for individual projects (November).
- Project Kickoff meeting (November).
- Splitting participants into two groups for "First Group Installation" and "Second Group Installation" (October/November).
- On-site "Training & Workshop" for each installation (November).
- Gathering data from all pilot installations and getting in touch with partners to understand system performance (January/February).
- Obtaining client feedback (February).
- Project Kickdown final report (March).

The bottom of the brochure features a "CREATE PUBLIC AWARENESS" section with a timeline from September to March, including "Workshop completes pilot documentation", "Gather feedback from participants", "Project kickoff", "First group installation", "Second group installation", "Validate technology", "Obtain client feedback", and "Project kickdown final report". It also includes contact information for Barcelona and London offices, logos for WorldSensing, SME Instrument, and the European Union, and a "Co-financed by the European Union" logo.

Aiming to establish a direct link between Worldsensing’s marketing team and the end-user’s requests, these surveys have not only focused on technical aspects but generic expectations regarding the ideal smart parking solution. The aggregated information has been used to prepare the final business models shown in Chapter 4. Survey responses are available at Annex II.

When?	Where?	Why?
April 2018	Barcelona (Spain)	Reports received from end-users

3.4 Contribution to roadmaps

Action	Comments
2.1-Number of contributions to roadmaps, discussion papers	Worldsensing collaborates with the Mobility department of Barcelona and Parking Sense (Los Angeles) to provide direct insight into the development of roadmaps for the adoption of “smart technologies” in these two cities.

Worldsensing established during the first period of the project a close interaction with the Mobility department of Barcelona to assist them in the definition of the city’s mobility roadmap. The goal is to create ecosystems of Internet of Things (IoT) in Barcelona: Worldsensing contributes with IoT devices installed in the streets for demo purposes and shares its experience in mobility management. This work has started during the action period, but it will continue in the future.

When?	Where?	Why?
May 2017	Barcelona (Spain)	Agreement on city roadmap preparation regarding mobility services

Parking Sense is the leading parking provider in the United States. As explained in the deliverable D5.1, it won a massive tender in 2016 to deploy 20.000 outdoor parking spots in the proximity of Los Angeles Metro stations, and Worldsensing was selected as a key technology provider. Nevertheless, the collaboration between the two entities is not limited to a mere exchange of sensors, but to a collaborative work that will end with concrete proposals for the LA Metro authorities to enhance the complex mobility status of the American city. This work has started during the second project period and it will continue in the future.

When?	Where?	Why?
January 2018	Los Angeles (USA)	Agreement to define the parking management roadmap in LA Metro areas

3.5 Contribution to policy-makers

Action	Comments
2.2-Number of contributions to policy-makers	(1) Collaboration with Buckinghamshire County Council and Interdigital Ltd. about the use of open mobility data in UK. (2) Joint-study with Barcelona authorities (BSM) to define policies about the use of parking spots (touristic coaches).

In the first project period, Worldsensing attended the “*Transport Data Initiative (TDI)*” to support the Buckinghamshire County Council (UK) policies definition about the use of open data. TDI is led by local authorities who believe that improving the way they collect, store, and use data will help to deliver improved transport services while reducing costs. TDI has fast established itself as a major player in the UK with representatives from over 40 different authorities, covering 70% of the UK population. Supported by an extensive network of transport specialists, TDI enables local authorities of all sizes and budgets to benefit from innovative solutions traditionally reserved to large urban areas. Worldsensing has actively collaborated with some British councils to define a meaningful use of open data to improve the citizens’ mobility. This action has been partially supported by the UK project OneTransport.

When?	Where?	Why?
March 2017	Manchester (UK)	Discussion about the use of Open Data to improve mobility service

In the second project period, Worldsensing was contacted by the authorities of Barcelona (*Serveis Municipals (B:SM)*¹) to assist them with the definition of new policies to organise the tourism in the city. BSM is an entity fully controlled by the Barcelona City Council. At present time, the activities that B:SM manages are extremely varied, ranging from mobility management to the operation of leisure facilities.

One of the main challenges that BSM faces is how to manage and monitor the massive volume of tourists visiting Barcelona. In close collaboration with Worldsensing, a novel system for monitoring the use of parking spaces reserved for the touristic bus on strategic points of the city (i.e. Sagrada Familia) has been envisaged by adding elements of Fastprk2. If everything goes well, the first proof-of-concept test will be conducted in September 2018, developing new policies for the parking spot use and payment.

When?	Where?	Why?
May 2018	Barcelona (Spain)	New system and policies for the management of touristic coaches in Barcelona.

¹ <https://www.bsmsa.cat/en/>

3.6 Number of web users

The content of the project website was explained in detail at the deliverable D6.1. In the second period, the website structure has remained unchanged. Gradually, more project-related contents have been published through the company's general channels to maximize the impact and advantage from a broader audience.

Action	Comments
3.1-Number of downloads of material from the web	The KPI for this action is 300 downloads. Taking a broad view, this figure has been far outweighed if the project videos are considered.

Three project videos have been produced in the frame of the project. Details given in below:

Video	Link	Period	Views ²
Project presentation	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JzKIC4UHwcE	1	752
Project main benefits and pilot introduction	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=b2zYNqVragU	2	221
Project interview with end-users and commercialization kick-off	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tqCElqIO-c8	2	422

Besides, some Open Data contents have been released in a dedicated area at ZENODO website³, which are getting further downloads, despite most of them were recently published.

Action	Comments
3.2-Number of registered members of the website	The project website the project does not have registration functionalities. This eliminates duplicated communication channels. Registered users are controlled through the Worldsensing main site.

The project website uses Google Analytics to record metrics on users and page views.

Google Analytics provides information on users and new sessions per month from the launch of the project website in July 2018. In total, there have been more than **9244 visits** to the site by **4925 different users** (100 new users per month). Drilling further into the available statistics, the site has been accessed by users from **90 different countries**. The figure below shows, using colour intensities, the origin of the visitors; the distribution across the world map shows that the site has attracted most interest in the United States and Spain (2297 & 1016 visits respectively).

² Figures on 13/08/2017

³ <https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=fastprk2>

Country ?	Acquisition		
	Users ?	New Users ? ↓	Sessions ?
	0 % of Total: 0.00% (0)	4,926 % of Total: 100.02% (4,925)	6,032 % of Total: 100.00% (6,032)
1. United States	0 (0.00%)	2,282 (46.33%)	2,297 (38.08%)
2. (not set)	0 (0.00%)	1,233 (25.03%)	1,234 (20.46%)
3. Spain	0 (0.00%)	405 (8.22%)	1,016 (16.84%)
4. India	0 (0.00%)	92 (1.87%)	124 (2.06%)
5. United Kingdom	0 (0.00%)	67 (1.36%)	105 (1.74%)
6. Italy	0 (0.00%)	63 (1.28%)	76 (1.26%)
7. Germany	0 (0.00%)	62 (1.26%)	68 (1.13%)
8. Canada	0 (0.00%)	54 (1.10%)	57 (0.94%)
9. Philippines	0 (0.00%)	44 (0.89%)	44 (0.73%)
10. Brazil	0 (0.00%)	43 (0.87%)	44 (0.73%)
11. France	0 (0.00%)	38 (0.77%)	52 (0.86%)
12. Netherlands	0 (0.00%)	33 (0.67%)	39 (0.65%)

(Country Not set means we can not locate the IP address)

Considering the Fastprk2 web analytics, we have seen as the number of visits increased a lot during the pilot phase – which means that our strict collaboration with the end-users has impacted the communication process of the Fastprk2 project.

3.7 Press releases

Action	Comments
3.3-Number of press releases issued	Fastprk2 team has actively worked to increase the awareness of the project among stakeholders. Several articles and blog posts have been published. The planned KPI was 4 posts, but this figure has been clearly overcome.

The final list of public press releases for the whole Fastprk2 project has been:

Title	Period	Date	Description
New funding: Worldsensing starts Fastprk2 project	1	Jun-16	http://www.fastprk2.eu/2016/06/01/worldsensing-starts-fastprk2-project/
The future Smart parking management system	1	Jun-16	http://www.fastprk2.eu/2016/06/15/great-support-center2/
Narrowband-IoT at Mobile World Congress 2017	1	Feb-17	http://www.fastprk2.eu/2017/02/27/narrowband-iot-mobile-world-congress-2017/
Innovation: Innovative IoT technology for the XII Business Congress at University of Barcelona	1	May-17	http://www.fastprk2.eu/2017/05/30/innovative-iot-technology-for-the-xii-business-congress-at-university-of-barcelona/
Fastprk2 project completes first year and delivers prototype	2	Aug-17	http://www.fastprk2.eu/2017/08/24/fastprk2-project-completes-first-year-delivers-prototype/
The top 3 features of the new Fastprk2 prototype	2	Sept-17	http://www.fastprk2.eu/2017/09/19/fastprk2-top-three-features-detection-algorithm/
NB-IoT - The future of smart parking systems	2	Nov-17	http://www.fastprk2.eu/2017/11/20/narrow-band-iot-future-smart-parking-systems/
Web Summit 2017 showcases EU high-tech SMES	2	Dec-17	http://www.fastprk2.eu/2017/12/01/innovation-web-summit-2017-eu-high-tech-smes/
Testing phase for Fastprk2 initiated in EU countries	2	Dec-17	http://www.fastprk2.eu/2017/12/01/innovation-testing-fastprk2-eu/
Deep Learning and smart parking	2	Feb-18	http://www.fastprk2.eu/2018/02/16/deep-learning-smart-parking/
Using Python to develop Fastprk2	2	Feb-18	http://www.fastprk2.eu/2018/02/28/using-python-develop-fastprk2/
Hackathon - Designing the future of Mobility	2	March-18	http://www.fastprk2.eu/2018/03/12/hackathon-mobility-iot-task-hackers/
Worldsensing at Intertraffic Amsterdam 2018	2	March-18	http://www.fastprk2.eu/2018/03/20/worldsensing-intertraffic-amsterdam-2018/
IPI 2018 - Official Fastprk evolution launch, part of the world's biggest parking project	2	May-18	http://www.fastprk2.eu/2018/05/31/ipi2018-fastprk-evolution-launch/
Smart Parking - Worldsensing rolls out Fastprk evolution	2	Jun-18	https://www.worldsensing.com/news/new-smart-parking-fastprk-evolution-2/

3.8 Domain exhibitions

Action	Comments
3.4-Number of domain exhibitions attended	Fastprk2 is a strategic project for Worldsensing. It has been presented in ten international events.

The first event attended by Worldsensing was the “*Smart City Expo World Congress 2016*” (SCEWC - <http://www.smartcityexpo.com/en/>), an international summit of discussion about the link between urban reality and the technological revolution. Some facts about the 2016 edition:

SCEWC'16: 16,688 visitors, 105 countries, 420 speakers, 591 exhibitors & 600 cities involved.

Worldsensing participated in SCEWC 2016 to discuss the product portfolio with potential clients and show the Fastprk2 project ambition. It was presented to more than 50 experts willing to adopt innovative IoT-technologies. This action was completed in the first project period.

When?	Where?	Why?
November 2016	Barcelona (Spain)	Smart City International Congress about innovative technology

The second event was the “Mobile World Congress 2017” (<https://www.mobileworldcongress.com/>), which is a combination of the world’s largest exhibition for the mobile industry and a conference featuring prominent executives representing mobile operators, device manufacturers, technology providers, vendors and content owners from all across the world. Some features about the 2017 edition:

Mobile World Congress’17: more than 108,000 attendants, professionals from 208 countries and 3,500 media members.

Regarding Fastprk2, Worldsensing collaborated with Telefonica to show a demo of NB-IoT technology. This action was completed in the first project period.

When?	Where?	Why?
February 2017	Barcelona (Spain)	Innovative technology interconnected with mobile network

The third event with Fastprk2 participation was the “IPI Conference & Expo 2017” (IPI - <http://ipiconference.parking.org>). It brought together more than 3,000 parking professionals from 35+ countries around the globe, representing every level of experience and segment of the parking and transportation industry. It delivered four days of exceptional education, the largest display of parking-specific technology and innovations, dozens of diverse networking chances, and the opportunity to connect with a global community. The IPI Conference & Expo provides the opportunity to develop both professional and personal skill sets offering the latest in technology; mobility and alternative transportation; enforcement, finance, and auditing curriculums; planning, design, and construction sessions; personal development and communications courses. In such a

scenario, Worldsensing aimed to identify, in an early stage, potential business opportunities for the Fastprk2 product. This action was completed in the first project period.

When?	Where?	Why?
May 2017	New Orleans (USA)	Presentation of Fastprk2 to potential clients

The first event attended during the second period of the project was the 2017 edition of the “Smart City Expo World Congress” More than 17.000 professional visitors attended the event, with over 600 exhibitors, along with high-level representatives from more than 700 cities and over 420 international speakers. An awareness campaign of the Fastprk2 main strengths was carried out in a dedicated space inside the Worldsensing booth.

When?	Where?	Why?
November 2017	Barcelona (Spain)	Presentation of Fastprk2 to potential clients

In November 2017, Fastprk2 attended the Web Summit 2017, held last November 6-9 in Lisbon (Portugal). Attendees from over 160 countries made this event the largest tech conference in the world. The summit exhibited the entire ecosystem of European entrepreneurship and featured key companies who have expanded operations outside the EU with the support of the Enterprise Europe Network (EEN or the Network). The EEN highlighted five European small and medium-sized

enterprises (SMEs) who were granted direct support for innovation efforts. Among them was Worldsensing and its project Fastprk2 were highlighted as a success story.

When?	Where?	Why?
November 2017	Lisbon (Portugal)	Presentation of Fastprk2 and meetings with innovators and potential partners

Again, February was the time for the Mobile World Congress (MWC), the world’s largest event for the mobile industry. With a more mature technology ready, the event was an excellent opportunity to close the first business operations of Fastprk2.

When?	Where?	Why?
February 2018	Barcelona (Spain)	One-to-one meetings with potential clients and partners to boost Fastprk2 project impact

Since 1972, Intertraffic Amsterdam has become the reference platform of choice for mobility professionals around the world. Once the pilot campaign was virtually completed and tangible results were available, the event was the “premiere” where the new product was fully shown.

When?	Where?	Why?
May 2018	Amsterdam (The Netherlands)	Present Fastprk2 to potential clients.

In June 2018, Worldsensing attended IPI Conference & Expo 2018 presenting the final version of the Fastprk2 product to expand its network and initiate the pure commercial activities. The brand-new results obtained at the LA pilot were highlighted.

When?	Where?	Why?
June 2018	Orlando (USA)	Present Fastprk2 to potential clients

Finally, in September 2018 Worldsensing will attend the EIC Innovators' Summit in Berlin. This event is an exceptional networking platform for companies to exchange experiences and explore new business opportunities. Under the motto

“Innovation Kitchen Europe”, Worldsensing is expecting to find a gourmet menu of engaging keynotes, curated workshops and enticing pitching sessions under an overall atmosphere of entrepreneurship and creativity.

When?	Where?	Why?
September 2018	Berlin (Germany)	Present Fastprk2 EC action as a whole

3.9 Conference papers and presentations

Action	Comments
4.1-Number of journal publications	According to the EC-GA, two publications were expected by the end of the project. This task has however been delayed focusing efforts on reaching the final product in due time. Nevertheless, the task is being taken up now with the writing of two manuscripts on NB-IoT technology and the use of radar for parking detection. Considering the typical peer-review periods, the accepted works are expected in a 6-month horizon.
Action	Comments
4.2-Number of conference papers and presentations	This point has been accomplished with four main presentations in heterogeneous events, fulfilling the KPI of the EC-GA

In October 2016, the Fastprk2 project was presented at Deutsche Telekom to create a partnership and define a concrete line of collaboration to deploy smart parking technology enriched with NB-IoT. Deutsche Telekom pushes the implementation and commercial expansion of the new, standardized and cost-effective NB-IoT technology across Europe. This action was completed in the first project period.

When?	Where?	Why?
October 2016	Bonn (Germany)	NB-IoT in Fastprk2 sensor

In the same month, a parallel collaboration scheme to exploit Fastprk2 sensor with NB-IoT was also defined with Telefonica; the first step was the technology demonstration at the “Mobile World Congress 2017”. This agreement was encompassed within the Telefonica-Huawei collaboration framework. This work was completed in the first project period.

When?	Where?	Why?
October 2016	Barcelona and Madrid (Spain)	NB-IoT in Fastprk2 sensor

In December 2016, Fastprk2 project was presented at the master in “Business Intelligence and Technological Innovation” as an example of future technology development for Business Intelligence in Smart mobility systems. This programme is

designed for new graduates who are embarking on the initial stages of their professional careers and want to work in the fields of ICT and Business Intelligence. This work was completed in the first project period.

When?	Where?	Why?
December 2016	Barcelona (Spain)	BI tools for Fastprk2 platform and services

The Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC) has organized the first edition of the Master's in Internet of Things (IoT), which puts together technological and innovation aspects. The master provides the ability to understand the market of the Internet of Things (IoT) and the future evolution, providing the necessary skills to design, implement and develop projects in this area. In April 2018, the Fastprk2 project was presented as a reference example of future technology developments for smart mobility systems. This action has been completed in the second project period.

When?	Where?	Why?
April 2018	Barcelona (Spain)	Fastprk2 as an example of IoT solution

3.10 Events attended

Action	Comments
4.3-Number of events attended	Several events have been attended by Worldsensing, in which Fastprk2 concepts were presented.

The first event with a Fastprk2 presentation was the “23rd World Smart Systems & Micromachine Summit 2017” (MMS 2017) in Barcelona (May 2017). The MMS 2017 was organized by the Iberian Delegation, and Worldsensing was highlighted as an innovative SME there. Fastprk2 was presented during the event since the special topic for that edition was “**Micro and Nano systems for Smart Cities applications**”. This action was completed during the first project period.

When?	Where?	Why?
May 2017	Barcelona (Spain)	Fastprk2 project presentation to European experts on physics and smart systems. A delegate from the European Commission attended the event.

The second event was the “XII Business Congress organized by the University of Barcelona” in May 2017. As a sponsor of the Business Congress, Worldsensing presented its innovation activities to highly-skilled and young students from the Faculty of Physics at the University of Barcelona. This contributed to raising the awareness about H2020. This action was completed during the first project period.

When?	Where?	Why?
May 2017	Barcelona (Spain)	Worldsensing presented Fastprk2 project to new talents at the University of Barcelona

The third event where the Fastprk2 project was presented was the **Ideathon** organized by Interdigital through the oneTRANSPORT project (<http://onetransport.uk.net/>).

The event brought together authorities and solution vendors to innovate in a way that regional needs are effectively addressed while offering a new distribution channel for the fast adoption of products at national and international scales. The preparatory work was done during the first period of Fastprk2, but it was implemented in the second one.

When?	Where?	Why?
June 2017	London (UK)	For the Ideathon, Worldsensing looked for the combination of multiple traffic datasets offered through open platforms

In July 2017, the engineering team of Worldensing worked a full week on cutting-edge ideas with a potential impact on the roadmap. In this week, the Fastprk2 project was presented and became a central topic (see deliverable D3.1).

When?	Where?	Why?
July 2017	Barcelona (Spain)	During the event a team of developers worked with cutting-edge Fastprk2 concepts

Python programming language is used as a reference technological tool within Worldensing. To share the experiences about how Fastprk2 project integrates Python code, Worldensing hosted the February event of the Barcelona Python Meetup Group (PyBCN) in the company’s headquarters.

When?	Where?	Why?
February 2018	Barcelona (Spain)	PyBCN organizes monthly meetups where members from the local Python community discuss about different topics, such as Fastprk2.

The University Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC) hosted the third edition of the Hackathon Mobility BCN, organized by CARNET⁴, the Open Hub for industrial and academic partners from the areas of automotive and mobility research & innovation initiated by SEAT, Volkswagen Group Research and UPC. While this year’s event encouraged hackers to focus on the future of urban mobility and autonomous driving and connected cars, the hackathon offered students to take part in one of three challenges to improve mobility in cities. As one of the local companies supporting the hackathon, Worldensing provided real-world parking management data from Fastprk2 and asked the participants to create a dashboard helping end-users, like parking operators, to make better and faster data-driven decisions.

⁴ <http://www.carnetbarcelona.com/>

When?	Where?	Why?
March 2018	Barcelona (Spain)	Fastprk2 project was presented and the data collected from the UPC pilot were shared and processed during the event.

Ecosummit accelerates smart green start-ups, investors and corporates. Their vision is to automate sustainability in energy, mobility and cities. At Ecosummit Berlin 2018, the organizers started fundraising the first smart green VC fund for the best smart green start-ups in Europe. Worldsensing’s CEO presented our vision of Smart City with special emphasize on the platform developed within the Fastprk2 project.

When?	Where?	Why?
May 2018	Barcelona (Spain)	Fastprk2 framework presented during the event by Worldsensing’s CEO

IMPACT Connected car launched its first open call in October 2017 where 500 startups and SMEs from more than 40 countries were selected. Later, 25 projects went through a “smartization programme” which started with a Disruptive Bootcamp held in Vigo (Spain) in April 2018. Finally, 15 companies (including Worldsensing) were selected for the “Ignition Plan”, the second stage of the IMPACT Connected Car program which will run until December 2018. During this programme, Worldsensing is performing a market research, the validation and feasibility studies, as well as developing business cases, business plans, SWOT analysis and go-to-market strategies to single out the most promising connected car approaches. This activity has been partially funded through a subgranting agreement. In the frame of all these actions, the results of Fastprk2 have been used as a starting point.

When?	Where?	Why?
June 2018	Vigo (Spain)	Fastprk2 results were used as a starting point of this programme

BPA’s Parkex is the Europe’s largest dedicated parking event. It provides a platform for leading industry suppliers and parking brands to launch and exhibit the latest cutting-edge products, technologies and services. Worldsensing parking expert, Toni Dantas was at #Parkex2018 on June 13-14 at The Ricoh Arena, Coventry, to present our leading outdoor parking management system enriched with Fastpark2 innovations.

When?	Where?	Why?
June 2018	Coventry (UK)	Fastprk2 framework was presented during Parkex event in UK

Considering IBM vision, IoT applications are relevant to a wide variety of needs and innovative technologies. These include such areas as personal safety and wellness; remote care; motion, bio-metric, and neuro-metric behavior tracking; and innovative forms of interactions. IBM team is composed of people with a variety of technical and research skills. Worldsensing, thanks to H2020-SMESEC project, has started a collaboration with IBM. Fastprk2 has been presented to IBM' staff in Haifa (Israel).

When?	Where?	Why?
June 2018	Haifa (Israel)	Fastprk2 framework was presented to IBM. The objective was to start a collaboration between the respective IoT departments

3.11 Business cases

Action	Comments
5.1-Number of business cases elaborated	The exploitation business cases have been prepared considering the inputs from the stakeholders and the analysis of the smart parking market. The business cases are presented in the chapter 4 of this deliverable.

3.12 Investors pitch

Action	Comments
5.2-Participation to venture capitals and business angels' events	Worldsensing has participated in different meetings with investors during the execution of Fastprk2 project.

These events have occurred during the first period of the project, before closing a Series B round of investment at company level. Details are given in the deliverable D6.1